

In the pursuit of equality for women plant breeders around the world

Ana Paola Valladares García^{1,*}, Akila Wijerathna-Yapa², Somyashree Mishra³, Md. Harun-Or-Rashid⁴, Mamta Nehra⁵, Vinita Ramtekey⁶, Ndah Renata Angwi⁷, Manu Maya Magar⁸, Dora Opondo⁹, Sasha¹⁰, Satish Kumar¹¹, Swati¹², Tanyaradzwa Tenesi¹³, Alison R. Bentley¹⁴, Bhoja Raj Basnet¹⁴

1. Arvalis - Institut du végétal, Baziège, France.
2. ARC Centre of Excellence for Plant Success in Nature and Agriculture, The University of Queensland, St Lucia, Australia.
3. Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Siksha 'O' Anusandhan Deemed to be University, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India.
4. International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT), Dhaka, Bangladesh.
5. Agriculture University, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India.
6. Indian Institute of Seed Science (ICAR), Mau, India.
7. University of Helsinki, Finland.
8. The UWA School of Agriculture and Environment, The University of Western Australia, Crawly, Australia & Nepal Agricultural Research Council, Kathmandu, Nepal.
9. Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organization (KALRO) Njoro, Kenya.
10. National Institute for Biotechnology and Genetic Engineering Faisalabad, Pakistan.
11. Indian Institute of Wheat & Barley Research (ICAR), Karnal, India.
12. Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar, India.
13. International Crops Research Institute for the Semi Arid Topics (ICRISAT), Bulawayo, Zimbabwe.
14. International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT), Texcoco, México.

* Contact: ap.valladaresgarcia@arvalis.fr

In the pursuit of equality for women plant breeders

Abstract

The UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UNESCO, 2021) indicates that only 33.3% of researchers around the world are women. As in many other scientific fields, women have braved the male-dominated world and contributed equally to the development of plant breeding. This article was conceptualized as a project from the CIMMYT's "Basic Wheat Improvement Course 2022" to open the conversation on how the cultural norms and community values had led to a tangible inequality in representation in plant breeding. We also aimed to address ways to deal with these barriers and to continue to encourage and support women in this field. In this report we highlight the findings from a series of interviews with female scientists working in plant breeding and synthesize the recommendations.

Introduction

The millions of women engaged in agriculture across the globe face different realities, opportunities, and challenges. Today, their roles are changing as part of the continually evolving social, environmental, cultural, and economic contexts they live in. The complexity of the factors which make up these contexts makes it challenging to design and implement interventions to improve gender equity in agriculture (Akter et al., 2017; Lastarria-Cornhiel et al., 2014). Nevertheless, women play a significant and crucial role in agricultural development and allied fields. Therefore, it is essential to promote "equal access" policies designed to bring opportunities for women to access land, capital, markets, education and development services to remedy gender gaps (J. A. Ashby & Polar, 2019).

If more women are educated, and are actively involved, in the field of agriculture, the rate of production in the agricultural sector is projected to increase (Palacios-Lopez, Christiaensen and Kilic, 2017). Current literature involving women in plant related fields shows the importance of women in agriculture mainly as farmers. However, one equally important contribution that has been neglected is women as leading scientists in plant breeding programs. Plant breeding, the science of driving creative processes to improve crops, becomes a pivotal instrument which, with the contribution of educated women, can lead to a rapid growth in the agricultural production sector and a subsequent increase in food security.

Therefore, this article analyzes the challenges for female breeders from the experiences of 12 interviewees from different countries, while pinpointing the possible solutions to promote gender equity in the crop breeding domain.

Interviews

To get insight into the current situation for women in plant breeding, in March 2022, we interviewed twelve female breeders around the world (3 from Africa, 8 from Asia and 1 from America) from different career stages and backgrounds. We asked five questions about their opinions, challenges, and their thoughts on how gender equality can be further enhanced in this specific field and here we show the synthesis from their answers.

Q1. What are the top 3 major challenges you are facing as a female breeder in your career?

According to our interviews, the major issues faced during their careers as female breeders are related to lack of support, work-life imbalance and male chauvinism. The lack of resources in terms of accessibility to the field area, laboratory facilities, funds for publications, funds for participation in conferences or/and training are also big barriers still present for half of these women. The allocation of lower research funding for women shows that nowadays male and female scientists are still not equally treated. Allocation of adequate funds for plant breeding research is vital to train plant breeders with modern technologies and new skills (Morris et al, 2006).

Apart from official responsibilities, female plant breeders often have to manage family responsibilities and this was the foremost difficult challenge outlined by all the interviewers. One remarked “Social structure still expects more time for family duties than research”. Every moment of their lives is about balancing responsibilities and expectations and doing it with a smile – at least in public.

Male chauvinism was another predominant issue that the correspondents have identified. They felt that they often do not get appreciation and recognition for their work from the person in charge, which reduces their morale and lack of trust in themselves.

Q2. What is your experience as a woman in plant breeding and have you ever faced any kind of discrimination in your career?

Nine of the twelve women interviewed have faced gender discrimination during their careers. Related to the previous answer, they highlighted that the reason for this discrimination was mostly due to being considered as the responsible of childcare and family issues. This prejudice leads to how their opinions or creative suggestions have been perceived in the science community or it has affected their opportunities to advance in their career. Such discrimination conveys gender harassment, which is the most common type of sexual harassment, and includes actions towards the impression that women do not belong in the workplace, which can finally and easily evolve to the other types of sexual harassment (as sarcastic, rude and double meaning comments) or even as unwanted sexual attention (Witze, 2018).

Q3. Do you think female breeders can contribute differently to food security and nutrition than male breeders? How?

When asked if they believe that women can contribute differently to food security challenges as compared to their male counterparts, all interviewers answered yes. They explained that women are especially attentive to quality traits (nutritional content, cooking time) and work more into detail, while men focus more on agronomic traits, for example. It is studied that women look for certain traits that make planting and harvesting easier regarding their roles and responsibilities in the value chain. Similar consideration that women prioritize food product quality traits while men prioritize agronomic traits has been reported by Teeken

et al, (2021). The interviewers also mentioned that “Women are also more likely to be attuned to the needs of women”. Thus, having both men and women equally involved in the breeding process could lead to the integration of different points of views and to making sure that women’s needs are represented.

Q4. What are three major improvements needed to encourage women to work as plant breeders?

The major issues for female plant breeders are related to childcare and family responsibilities where females are still considered as the main person to play the main role. The biological nature of female to childbirth cannot be shifted but a supportive work environment with flexible working hours for females following childbirth can be helpful. The provision of childcare facilities at the workplace, paid maternity leaves, in addition with paid paternity leaves will help female breeders to lessen the burden, faster recovery and return to work. The equal opportunity in capacity building training and workshops, facilities for project collaborations and research grants accompanied by a warm working environment can boost the confidence of female breeders and help them to contribute at their best. They also emphasized that better policies along with awareness sessions should be arranged to address issues such as male chauvinism, gender inequality, sexual harassment, etc. in research communities.

Q5. As a woman in plant breeding, what is your opinion about working from home which came up due to the COVID-19 pandemic?

In response to their experience of working from home due to COVID-19 pandemic, most of these female breeders described it as challenging. As stated by one of the correspondents “Working from home is not an easy task as a woman because then the duty is doubled, and the work efficiency is less”. This refers to dealing with work deadlines while also dealing with increased household responsibilities.

Discussion

As seen from the answers to these questions, gender gaps still exist for women in plant breeding. However, these women – and many others – have embraced all the difficulties with their abilities and determination to overcome these issues. Nevertheless, we need to act upon these gender obstacles and use them as motives as to transform into a more supportive society and scientific community filled with new possibilities. We must address the causes of gender inequality, transforming power dynamics and looking to change the family conception towards the responsibilities laid on women. To tackle gender inequality for improved agricultural yields, it is needed to include gender-specific support to close the gap, ensure equal income distribution and education. These include deliberate women empowerment strategies through training and support for balancing their personal and work lives through improving national policies and public support to finance women's careers (Galiè et al., 2017; Halewood et al., 2007; Nchanji et al., 2021).

In many parts of the world the road to gender-equality starts from gender-responsiveness – acknowledging and addressing the root causes of gender inequality. Several institutions, organizations and programmes are adopting gender-responsive approaches and developing strategies that unveil and address the reduced access to breeding technologies, training, inclusion in decision-making and a plethora of other opportunities. Gender-responsive participatory plant breeding (PPB) is a helpful approach in the emerging mosaic of efforts to meet these current and future challenges (Colley et al., 2022; Gibson et al., 2011; Halewood et al., 2007). As an example of these efforts, CGIAR Excellence in Breeding (EiB) institution, to enhance the adoption of new varieties, has liaised its product profile platform with G+ customer profiles characterizing client groups targeted for new varieties and gender-based factors that influence adoption like knowledge, assets and decision-making. CGIAR Gender and Breeding Initiatives defined strategies that offer equal opportunities to women in breeding and food systems (CGIAR, 2022).

Awards by different institutions boost the visibility of women's achievements in breeding, encouraging women to pursue STEM careers for breeding. For example, Women in Triticum Early Career Award by The Borlaug Global Rust Initiative (BGRI) and Women in Plant Mutation Breeding Award by The International Atomic Energy Agency. Additionally, The World Food Prize Foundation has recognized different women researchers, as Dr. Hale Ann Tufan, winner of 2019 Norman E. Borlaug Field Research and Application Award and pioneer of gender-responsive breeding across the globe; and Maria Andrade, 2016 World Food Prize co-winner, who developed biofortified, orange-fleshed sweet potato which is a staple in Sub-Saharan Africa (World Food Prize.org).

Further, it is imperative for international organizations, national breeding programmes, NGOs and research institutions to shift to gender-relevant policies, to ensure equality in decision-making power, rights, access to decent work, services, markets and control over resources, and reduction in women's work burden (FAO, 2020). The FAO Policy on Gender Equality 2020-2030 includes targeted interventions and 17 minimum standards of gender mainstreaming to address the constraints of gender-based discrimination faced by women in its organisation, and agriculture and food systems across the globe (FAO, 2020).

Conclusion

Careers for women in agricultural science and particularly in plant breeding are still an uphill challenge. Women are indispensable for food security and improved nutrition. However, socio-economic and political differences that characterize gender inequality prevent women from equally accessing resources and opportunities, contributing and reaping the full benefits of their work. Identifying and addressing the root causes of gender inequality, employing gender-responsive breeding approaches and engaging women in policymaking are strategies that have seen great improvements in breeding. It is in our hands to tackle the discussed obstacles for future generations and to keep supporting women to take active roles in this promising field.

Acknowledgments

Special thanks to Dr. Damaris A. Odeny and Ms. Mercy Wamalwa from Kenya; Dr. Caroline Sichalwe from Tanzania; Ms. Pratikshya Shrestha and Ms. Bihani Thapa from Nepal; Dr. Bhavana Patnayakuni from India; Ms. Tanushree Halder from Bangladesh; Dr. Lu LU from China; Ms. Bao Linh Ton from Vietnam; Dr. Rizwana Maqbool and Dr. Sundas Shahzad from Pakistan and Dr. Margaret Krause from USA.

References

- Akter, S., Rutsaert, P., Luis, J., Htwe, N. M., San, S. S., Raharjo, B., & Pustaka, A. (2017). Women's empowerment and gender equity in agriculture: A different perspective from Southeast Asia. *Food Policy*, 69, 270–279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2017.05.003>
- Ashby, J. A., & Polar, V. (2019). The implications of gender relations for modern approaches to crop improvement and plant breeding. In *Gender, Agriculture and Agrarian Transformations*. Routledge.
- CGIAR Excellence in Breeding Platform. (2021). Breeding scientists are women of their word. *Excellenceinbreeding*. <https://excellenceinbreeding.org/blog/breeding-scientists-are-women-their-word>
- CGIAR Excellence in Breeding Platform. (2022). G+ Tools for gender-responsive breeding <https://www.cgiar.org/innovations/g-tools-for-gender-responsive-breeding/>. Retrieved 22 November 2022
- Colley, M. R., Tracy, W. F., Lammerts van Bueren, E. T., Diffley, M., & Almekinders, C. J. M. (2022). How the Seed of Participatory Plant Breeding Found Its Way in the World through Adaptive Management. *Sustainability*, 14(4), 2132. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14042132>
- CropLife International. (2018). Empowering Women through Plant Breeding. *CropLife International*. <https://croplife.org/news/empowering-women-through-plant-breeding/>
- Doss, C., Meinzen-Dick, R., Quisumbing, A., & Theis, S. (2018). Women in agriculture: Four myths. *Global Food Security*, 16, 69–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2017.10.001>
- FAO. (2020). *FAO Policy on Gender Equality 2020–2030*. Rome. <https://www.fao.org/3/cb1583en/cb1583en.pdf>
- FAO. (2011). *The state of food and agriculture, 2010-2011: Women in Agriculture: closing the gender gap for development*. FAO. <https://www.fao.org/publications/card/en/c/99f234e5-fac5-5a06-8964-b455b4ffe721/>
- Fromm, I. (2019). Why the inclusion of women's perception in plant breeding programs is critical: An example from India. *Horticulture International Journal*, Volume 3(Issue 5). <https://doi.org/10.15406/hij.2019.03.0013>

- Galiè, A., Jiggins, J., Struik, P. C., Grando, S., & Ceccarelli, S. (2017). “Women’s empowerment through seed improvement and seed governance: Evidence from participatory barley breeding in pre-war Syria”. *NJAS - Wageningen Journal of Life Sciences*, 81, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.njas.2017.01.002>
- Gibson, R. W., Mpembe, I., & Mwanga, R. O. M. (2011). Benefits of participatory plant breeding (PPB) as exemplified by the first-ever officially released PPB-bred sweet potato cultivar. *The Journal of Agricultural Science*, 149(5), 625–632. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021859611000190>
- Halewood, M., Deupmann, P., Sthapit, B. R., Vernooy, R., & Ceccarelli, S. (2007). Participatory plant breeding to promote Farmers’ Rights. 8.
- IAEA. (2021). Global Success in Plant Breeding Celebrated with New Achievement Awards. International Atomic Energy Agency. <https://www.iaea.org/newscenter/news/global-success-in-plant-breeding-celebrated-with-new-achievement-awards>
- Lastarria-Cornhiel, S., Behrman, J. A., Meinzen-Dick, R., & Quisumbing, A. R. (2014). Gender Equity and Land: Toward Secure and Effective Access for Rural Women. In A. R. Quisumbing, R. Meinzen-Dick, T. L. Raney, A. Croppenstedt, J. A. Behrman, & A. Peterman (Eds.), *Gender in Agriculture: Closing the Knowledge Gap* (pp. 117–144). Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-8616-4_6
- Lilienfeld, E., Nicholas, P. K., Breakey, S., & Corless, I. B. (2018). Addressing climate change through a nursing lens within the framework of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. *Nursing Outlook*, 66(5), 482–494. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.outlook.2018.06.010>
- Liu, Q.-Q., Yu, M., & Wang, X.-L. (2015). Poverty reduction within the framework of SDGs and Post-2015 Development Agenda. *Advances in Climate Change Research*, 6(1), 67–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.accre.2015.09.004>
- Morris, M., Edmeades, G., & Pehu, E. (2006). The global need for plant breeding capacity: What roles for the public and private sectors? *HortScience*, 41(1), 30-39. <https://journals.ashs.org/hortsci/view/journals/hortsci/41/1/article-p30.xml?rskey=JJ4DYU>
- Nchanji, E. B., Collins, O. A., Katungi, E., Nduguru, A., Kabungo, C., Njuguna, E. M., & Ojiewo, C. O. (2021). What Does Gender Yield Gap Tell Us about Smallholder Farming in Developing Countries? *Sustainability*, 13(1), 77. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13010077>
- Palacios-Lopez, A., Christiaensen, L., & Kilic, T. (2017). How much of the labor in African agriculture is provided by women? *Food Policy*, 67, 52–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODPOL.2016.09.017>
- Teeken, B., Garner, E., Agbona, A., Balogun, I., Olaosebikan, O., Bello, A., Madu, T., Okoye, B., Egesi, C., Kulakow, P., & Tufan, H. A. (2021). Beyond “Women’s Traits”: Exploring How Gender, Social Difference, and Household Characteristics Influence Trait Preferences. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 5. <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fsufs.2021.740926>
- UNESCO. (2021). UNESCO research shows women career scientists still face gender bias. Retrieved November 19, 2022, from <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/unesco-research-shows-women-career-scientists-still-face-gender-bias>
- Witze, A. (2018). Sexual harassment is rife in the sciences, finds landmark US study. *Nature* 558, 352-353. Retrieved April 5, 2022, from <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-05404-6>
- Worldfoodprize.org (n/a). Digital dialogue: March 24 | She Who Provides. Retrieved November 24, 2022, from https://www.worldfoodprize.org/en/digital_dialogue/march_24_she_who_provides/